

FROM COCRYSTAL DESIGN TO DRUG SHELF: NOVEL PREPARATION METHODS AND MARKETED PHARMACEUTICAL PRODUCTS

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Abstract: A possible technique to increase the solubility of BCS Classes II & IV medications that are poorly soluble is pharmaceutical cocrystallization. The benefits of cocrystallization on the stability and rate of medication dissolution are not well known to most scientists. Evidence was compiled from a range of articles utilizing Medline, Pubmed, Embase, Scopus, Google Scholar, and Web of Science in an organised and succinct manner. This paper addresses cocrystallization technology, products that have been marketed using this strategy, and problems associated with these processes. The most popular and successful method for cocrystal synthesis is laser irradiation. Other novelistic or contemporary methods for producing cocrystals include hot melt extrusion, spray evaporation, super critical fluid dynamic technology, and irradiation. The several in-vitro assessment parameters used to assess the cocrystals and their drug release are also included in this publication. It also explains the numerous innovative and conventional methods of producing medicinal cocrystals, as well as the reasons behind the interest of researchers and the pharmaceutical industry in cocrystals. Pharmaceutical crystals are currently thought to be critically needed for medical or scientific purposes. The countless reviews and research articles that have been published in various periodicals over the past 10 years clearly demonstrate this. In recent years, a number of pharmaceutical companies have begun asserting patents worldwide. These companies are growing rapidly because of the laws and the link to intellectual property. Pharmaceutical crystals are an essential and useful tool for raising the stability, melting point, and bioavailability of medications.

Key Words: Cofomer, physicochemical properties, preformulation, cocrystals.

1. Introduction

Solubility and the rate at which it dissolves are the primary determinants of the active chemical moiety's effectiveness and activity. Cocrystals have greatly improved the physicochemical characteristics of medicinal compounds, and this has piqued the interest of researchers in the modern period. The conventional approach to drug development relied on fortuitous findings or conventional treatments. But during the past 20 years, there has been an increasing emphasis on logical design and combination of medicine(s), leading to the rise of drug candidate development. Many novel medication targeting techniques have been developed for effectiveness. In order to create better therapeutic molecules, potential drug molecules have been synthesized and contemporary methods such as combinatorial chemistry and High-Throughput Screening (HTS) have been employed^[1]. According to the US Food and Drug Administration, cocrystals are defined as crystalline substances composed of two or more non-identical molecules in a comparable crystal lattice, which are often drug substances and crystal formers or co-formers. A precise definition of cocrystal is still up for debate, notwithstanding the USFDA's definition. Drug material and co-formers are added at a stoichiometric ratio (resultant equals the total moles of drug material and co-formers) for the purpose of manufacturing cocrystals. The cocrystals are defined in the Paul Pfeiffer textbook and are classified into two groups according to where they came from: One type of crystal is composed entirely of biological components, whilst the other is composed entirely of inorganic components. Natural: Organic or active moiety can co-form with inorganic methods, and vice versa^[2]. In contrast, coformer and API in another type should only be organic. Co-crystals, which are multicomponent compounds generated within the surrounding of molecules or charged active ingredients, are discovered to be in a solid state in ambient conditions (Figure 1). Industrial R&D (Research & Development) experts are now researching on medication formulation employing cocrystal methods to increase or enhance class II drugs' aqueous solubility in the BCS classification, as these drugs have good permeability but low solubility^[3,4].

Figure 1: Salts, Cocrystals, and Hydrates/Solvates Schematically

Salts: A crystal with two ions or more is called salt.

Solvate: Any crystal that has two ions or more and a solvent molecule is called a solvate.

Cocrystals: A cocrystal is a crystal that has two ions or more in addition to one coformer molecule^[5].

APIs can be found in both crystalline and amorphous solid forms, such as polymorphs, hydrates, solvates, cocrystals, and salts. Seldom is the occurrence of polymorphs and the development of salts, cocrystals, solvates, and hydrates predicted (Figure 2)^[6].

Figure 2: Types of Solid API's Available

2. Medicines Available in Market with Co-crystallization Technique

Esteve Pharmaceutical produced E-58425, a recently licensed medication that is already on the market. It is a combination of two medications, Tramadol and Celecoxib, and is designed to relieve acute pain associated with gout and osteoarthritis. A medication called Entresto, a combination of sacubitril sodium and valsartan sodium, was also authorized by the FDA in 2015. The formulation's usage of valsartan inhibits the type I (AT1) Angiotensin receptor, and sacubitril is a prodrug metabolite. This cocrystal mixture helps patients live longer without experiencing any cardiac damage and helps avoid several forms of heart failure^[7].

Dimenhydrinate, a medication that is currently used extensively to treat vertigo and motion sickness, is created by mixing 8-chlorotheophylline with diphenhydramine. As is well known, diphenhydramine has antihistamine and mildly cholinergic effects. Eight-chlorotheophylline is used to counteract the drowsiness that comes with antihistaminic activity, and these two effects work together to prevent nausea, vomiting, motion sickness, and vertigo^[8].

Depakote is one of the greatest medications on the market, and it's used extensively because it works so well. This medication's combination of valproic acid and sodium valproate is used to treat epilepsy, seizures, and mild depression. Valproic acid has relatively little water solubility, however co-crystallization enhances its physicochemical characteristics and lessens its adverse effects. Valproic acid has a variety of pharmacological effects, including blocking voltage-gated ion channels, directly affecting the amount of aminobutyric acid in the central nervous system, and inhibiting histone deacetylase^[9].

Dichloralphenazone, a commonly used muscle relaxant in the form of a crystal, is a 1:2 mixture of NSAIDs, namely antipyrine and chloral hydrate. As a COX inhibitor, antipyrine blocks the actions of COX-1, COX-2, and COX-3, the enzymes involved in prostaglandin formation. This combination medication is intended to treat or prevent tension-related headaches, such as migraine headaches (Table 1)^[10].

Table 1: Products on the Market Using the Co-Crystallization Process

S.NO.	Marketed Name	Composition of Drug	Pharmacological Uses
1	Dimenhydrinate	Diphenhydramine + 8-chlorotheophylline	Motion Sickness, Nausea, Vomiting.
2	Depakote	Sodium Valproate + Valproic Acid	Epilepsy & Bipolar Disorder And to prevent Migraine Headache
3	E-58425	Tramadol (44mg) + Celecoxib (56mg)	Acute Pain
4	Dichloralphenazone	Antipyrene + Chloral Hydrate (1:2)	Migraine And Tension Associated Headache
5	Entresto	Sacubitril (49mg) + Valsartan (51mg)	Treat certain type of heart failure (Angiotensin Receptor Blocker)
6	Suglat	Ipraglidlozin + L-Prolin	Hyper-Glycemic
7	Lexapro	Escitalopram + Oxalate	Anti-Depressant
8	Beta Chlor	Chloral Hydrate + Betaine	Short-term treatment of Insomnia

3. Methods of co-crystallization

Cocrystals may be made using a variety of techniques, which can be generally divided into two groups: solution-based and solid-state based. Each approach has benefits and drawbacks of its own. Solid state procedures offer a practical, adaptable, sustainable, and environmentally responsible way to manufacture cocrystals, and they are useful for both laboratory and commercial fabrication of crystals. Because they are straightforward, easy to monitor, and control over the final product, solution-based methods are primarily limited to and useful for the preparation of cocrystals on a laboratory scale. However, caution must be exercised as the choice of solvent can have an impact on the properties of the cocrystals^[11] (Figure 3).

SOLID-STATE METHODS OF COCRYSTALLIZATION

Hot-melt Extrusion Method

HME is a technique or procedure for producing products with consistent size and shape. It starts with the raw material being conveyed under a certain temperature using a revolving screw. Using heat to melt the coformer and API, the hot melt extrusion (HME) technique is a cutting-edge technology that has been utilized to generate pharmaceutical cocrystals. The hot melt extrusion process was once employed to produce food items and polymers, but it has now been shown to be the most effective way to produce medicinal dosage forms^[12-15].

Contact Formation

Cocrystals develop on their own when API and conformer are combined in a regulated air environment. There is no need for mechanical force. Pure components are ground in a few of the circumstances.

The rate rose with increasing temperature and relative humidity. According to Ibrahim et al., there would be more cocrystal formation in the range of 20 to 45 μm if the particle size dispersion is smaller.

Three phases of the cocrystallization mechanism in moisture are deliquescent: Absorption of moisture, Reactant, dissolution, nucleation and development of cocrystals^[16,17].

Figure 3: Different Methods of cocrystallization

Dry/Neat Grinding

In this cocrystallization process, pharmacological active molecules (API) and conformers are combined in a solid, dry state, and pressure is applied either mechanically (using a mortar and pestle) or manually (using an automated ball mill).

It is called melt crystallization if the initial solid material is melted while being ground. In order

to prevent the material from melting, the temperature is also checked.

Solid state grinding has an advantage over solution-based methods in that its solubility prevents yield loss in solvent^[18-20].

Problems with the dry grinding include:

- Inability to create a cocrystal.
- Inadequate conversion to crystal: The result contains more beginning material than needed. This makes it more likely that an incomplete conversion to cocrystal will happen, which is undesirable since it increases the amount of purification required to get a pure cocrystal product. This issue can be solved by lengthening the grinding period, although this might lead to nonstoichiometric cocrystal formation.
- The formation of crystalline faults is possible if some amorphous content did. Use the molar equivalent and excess of each starting material to finish the dry grinding process. If a system exists, this may result in the favorite finding of an alternative crystal^[21-23].

High-Shear wet Granulation

The high-shear wet granulation method is key in **cocrystallization**. It combines two or more molecules into one crystal. This method uses strong shear forces to make granules, which are vital for cocrystal products.

The success of this method in **cocrystallization** depends on several factors. The shear forces mix and disperse the materials well. This ensures the **cocrystallization** partners are in close contact. A binder solution also helps in forming the granules, leading to the cocrystal structure^[24,25].

Advantages & Disadvantages

The high-shear wet granulation method has big benefits for the pharmaceutical world. It makes drug compounds better by improving their physical and chemical properties. This leads to drugs that work better and are more effective.

This method also makes production faster and cheaper. It cuts down on waste and makes products more consistent. This means companies can save money and get their products to market quicker.

But, this method has its downsides too. It's a bit tricky to get right, needing careful attention to things like how hard it mixes, temperature, and moisture. If these aren't just right, problems can happen like clumping or uneven quality. So, it's crucial to test and check the product thoroughly.

- Improved drug properties: enhanced solubility, stability, and bioavailability
- Increased production efficiency: reduced processing steps, minimized waste, and improved consistency
- Process complexity: requires careful optimization of parameters to avoid issues like agglomeration or undesirable changes in crystal structure
- Need for extensive characterization and testing to ensure quality and reproducibility^[26-29].

SOLUTION-BASED METHODS OF COCRYSTALLIZATION

Evaporative Cocrystallization

In the world of *pharmaceutical cocrystals* and *crystal engineering*, the solvent evaporation method is key. It uses *supramolecular chemistry* to create cocrystals. These cocrystals have better properties because of *hydrogen bonding* and *pi-stacking interactions*.

This method works by slowly removing the solvent. This lets the components form a cocrystal structure. It's great for making cocrystals that are more soluble, stable, and easier to use in medicine.

The solvent evaporation method is easy to use and can be scaled up. You can adjust things like temperature and solvent mix to get the right cocrystal. But it can be tricky to get the exact cocrystal form you want^[30,31].

Table 2: Advantages & Disadvantages of Evaporative method

Advantages	Limitations
Simplicity of the process	Potential for polymorphism
Scalability for industrial applications	Careful control over the crystallization process is required
Ability to control cocrystal formation through parameter adjustment	Limited understanding of the complex interplay between solvents, solutes, and cocrystal formation
Exploitation of non-covalent interactions like hydrogen bonding and pi-stacking ^[32-35] .	

Isothermal slurry conversion

This is the cocrystallization screening and scale-up technique with the highest efficiency. Using this technique, the conformer and API are dissolved in separate solutions at the right temperature and given the necessary amount of time to stir. Then, the constituent concentration is greater than the conformer's critical activity, allowing nucleation growth and crystal formation^[36-38].

Reaction Crystallization

This approach used a solution containing reactants to produce the cocrystals. When added to another solution and agitated in a vessel, the concentration in the combination surpasses the solubility, causing crystals to form. This kind of approach often involves rapid reactions and mixing conditions that affect crystal size. The expansion of nucleation is dependent on mixing at the microstate level, which results in supersaturation and decreases solubility. It promotes crystal formation by enabling nucleation^[39,40].

Cooling crystallization

A significant amount of reactant and solvent are combined in a reactor-jacketed vessel. To ensure that every solute is completely dissolved in the solvent, the mixture is heated to a high temperature and then cooled.

The crystal experiences hyper saturation at lower temperatures, leading to the precipitation of the crystal. The lattice route and component supersaturation level analysis may be used to determine the ideal operating parameters for the cooling crystallization process^[41,42].

Liquid Assisted Grinding

A very little quantity of solvent is introduced to the solid medication prior to grinding. The solvent has a catalytic function in the production of cocrystals and should be maintained throughout the grinding process. The kinetics of cocrystal formation are increased by solvent, however this is yet unclear. The reaction is accelerated by the solvent component.

by soaking the solid surface in kinetics. By adding methanol to an equimolar mixture of benzoic acid and carboxylic acid in a mortar, benzoic acid crystals were created [49]. After 30 minutes of grinding at 30 Hz with 50µl of nitromethane added, a 1:1 cocrystal combination of caffeine and tetrafluoro succinic acid was produced. Solvent drop grinding cocrystallization was used to produce a highly water soluble cocrystal of the weakly soluble nutraceutical hesperetin (HESP)^[43-46].

SUPERCRITICAL FLUID BASED TECHNIQUES

This method allows us to create particles in a single step while modifying morphology and size reduction. This is the best method for cocrystallization where the best quality crystals may be

obtained. CO₂ is the most widely used supercritical fluid; its benefits include fewer processing steps, being an environmentally friendly solvent, well-finished products (without solvent), a higher propensity for solubility, and, most importantly, less product degradation due to the fluid's lower temperatures (31 °C, 7.39 MPa)^[47-49].

Expanding Supercritical Solution Quickly (Rapid Expansion of Supercritical Solution)

One method for creating tiny microparticle crystals is to rapidly expand the supercritical solution. In supercritical fluid CO₂, the conformer and API solution are depressurized under atmospheric conditions, and the solvent fluid eventually decreases to supersaturation in the supercritical CO₂. Eventually, nucleation growth brought on by supersaturation forms the crystals. Using this approach, letrozole's solubility was increased 7.1 times. This method's disadvantages include low yields and the fact that only select pairings of conformer–drug combinations are soluble in CO₂. There is no need to add additional organic solvents because CO₂ functions as a solvent in the supercritical solvent crystallization procedure. In this process, the solvent induces intermolecular contacts that result in crystal nucleation, growth, and formation^[50]. This approach has the advantage of being able to be executed without the need for drying processes. By varying the temperature and pressure (of CO₂), solubility may be changed^[51]. A high product yield of crystals of carbamazepine including saccharin, theophylline, and indomethacin was achieved. Because there is no water involved in this process, it has the benefit of preventing the production of solvates and hydrates in the crystals. It is restricted to the creation of single-component crystals^[52-55].

Supercritical Anti-Solvent Method

Because of its higher miscibility towards organic solvents and lower solvent power towards conformer and API, CO₂ functions as an antisolvent in the supercritical anti-solvent approach. A polar organic solvent that dissolves the API and conformer in it is ethanol, also known as acetone^[56]. The fluid expands the volume and decreases the solubility, leading to supersaturation forms of the cocrystals^[57]. This can be achieved by inducing the solution containing the API and conformer into the high-pressure vessel containing supercritical CO₂ fluid or by using alternative methods, such as spraying the solution into the precipitation chamber^[58,59].

4. Techniques used for characterization of cocrystals

FOURIER-TRANSFORM INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY

Infrared spectroscopy, sometimes referred to as IR spectroscopy or vibrational spectroscopy, is the study of how infrared light interacts with materials through absorption, emission, or reflection. This method is used to study and identify chemical compounds or functional groups in solid, liquid, or gaseous states. It may be used to find and authenticate known and unknown samples, as well as categorize novel materials. The infrared spectroscopy process or procedure is carried out using a piece of equipment called an infrared spectrometer (sometimes called a spectrophotometer), which produces an infrared spectrum. A graph that displays the wavelength, frequency, or wavenumber on the horizontal axis and the absorbance (or transmittance) of infrared light on the vertical can be used to illustrate an IR spectrum. The most often used wavenumber unit in infrared spectra is reciprocal centimeters, or cm⁻¹. Infrared wavelength measurements are commonly stated in units of micrometres, or "microns," denoted by the sign "m," which are reciprocally related to wave number. Typical laboratory equipment that uses this method is an FTIR (Fourier transform infrared) spectrometer. Two-dimensional IR is also possible^[60,61].

SOLID-STATE NUCLEAR MAGNETIC RESONANCE

Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy, often known as magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS) or NMR spectroscopy, is a spectroscopic technique for studying the local magnetic fields around atomic nuclei. Sensitive radio receivers detect the nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) signal, which is produced when radio waves excite the sample's nuclei while it is in a magnetic field. The resonance frequency of a molecule may be changed by its intermolecular magnetic field, which can provide details about the electronic structure and different functional groups of the molecule. Since the fields are distinctive or extremely specific to individual compounds, NMR spectroscopy is the sole accurate method available in modern organic chemistry for identifying monomolecular organic molecules^[62].

- The NMR concept is usually composed of three sequential processes: The polarization of magnetic nuclear spins under an applied magnetic field B_0 ^[63].
- The modification of this nuclear spin alignment brought about by a weakly oscillating magnetic field and a radio-frequency (RF) pulse^[64].
- Identification and examination of the electromagnetic waves that the sample's nucleus produces as a result of this disturbance^[65].

In a similar manner, biochemists use NMR to find complex molecules such as proteins. In addition to molecular identification, NMR spectroscopy provides detailed information on the structure, dynamics, reaction state, and chemical environment of molecules. The most common NMR spectroscopies are carbon-13 and proton, however they may be applied to any material containing spin-containing nuclei^[66].

THERMAL GRAVIMETRY METHOD

The differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) thermo analytical technique is used to determine, as a function of temperature, the difference in the amount of heat required to raise the temperature of a sample relative to a reference. The sample and reference are maintained at almost the same temperature throughout the duration of the experiment. The temperature programme for a DSC research is typically designed such that the temperature of the sample holder increases linearly with time. The reference sample should have a well-established heat capacity throughout the range of temperatures to be scanned^[67].

Heat-flux DSC, one of the two main types of DSC (also known as Multi-Cell DSC), measures the differential in heat fluxes between a sample and a reference. The variation between the power supplied to the sample and a reference is also assessed using Power Differential Static Calculation.

From metals and simple chemicals to polymers and medicines, DSC is frequently used to assess a wide range of characteristics in both organic and inorganic materials^[68].

Among the characteristics measured are:

Glass transitions Phase modifications

Melting

Crystallization

Stability of product

Cure/kinetics of the cure

Stability of oxidation

Measurements of heat capacity, heat of fusion, etc^[69,70].

UV SPECTROSCOPY

Absorption spectroscopy or reflectance spectroscopy in the ultraviolet and the whole, surrounding visible portions of the electromagnetic spectrum is referred to as UV spectroscopy, often called UV-visible spectrophotometer (UV-Vis or UV/Vis). This method is popular in both theoretical and practical applications since it is inexpensive and simple to apply. For the sample, only chromophores that absorb in the UV visible range are suitable. Fluorescence spectroscopy is enhanced by absorption spectroscopy. Along with the wavelength of measurement, other significant factors include absorbance (A), transmittance (%T), and reflectance (%R), as well as how each of these varies over time^[71].

The quantitative assessment of many different analytes or samples, such as transition metal ions, highly conjugated organic compounds, and biological macromolecules, is accomplished through the widespread use of UV-Vis spectroscopy in analytical chemistry. While solids, gases, and liquids may all be analyzed using spectroscopy^[72].

HANSEN SOLUBILITY STUDY

The Hansen solubility parameters can be used to predict the solvent-solute affinity. The cohesion energy of mixtures that are distinguished by the Hansen solubility parameter (HSP) consists of three forces: hydrogen bonding, dipole, and London dispersion forces. The HSP value is used in many research areas, such as evaluating the solubility of solids in solvent, the compatibility and affinity of polymers in solvent, and the dispersability of small particles in solvent. However, the physical properties of the solvent, such as its permittivity, dipole moment, surface tension, and refractive index, may be used to decide which of the HSP techniques is appropriate for a certain liquid or mixture of liquids^[73].

DISSOLUTION STUDY

To maintain product quality, stability, and batch-to-batch uniformity, dissolution testing is a crucial analytical process that must be included in the final release investigation for solid oral dosage forms^[74].

Dissolution of the dosage form after swallowing, or the rate at which the active component is released into the body, is an important aspect of medication research since oral solid dosage forms are still the most prevalent way that pharmaceuticals are delivered. "To control product quality, stability, and batch-to-batch consistency, dissolution testing is a crucial analytical procedure that is required as part of the final release investigation for solid oral dosage forms." Dissolution tests and related acceptance criteria should aim to identify batches with inadequate bioavailability since the rate of dissolution can have a substantial impact on bioavailability^[75].

During the early phases of development, the main purpose of a dissolving test is to evaluate the therapeutic effectiveness, bioequivalence, and bioavailability of API. Dissolution testing is also utilized for quality control in later phases of the development process. A dissolving test assesses the product's performance by using a device that meets the acceptance requirements and has certain test circumstances^[76].

STABILITY STUDY

This makes it one of the most compelling factors for assessing the co-crystals as it takes into account the different climatic storage conditions and half-lives of the medication and its associated products. Calculating the half-life of the co-crystals and products under varied storage conditions involves conducting the inquiry for a predefined period of time at a certain temperature and humidity level. Additional variables like temperature, light, and humidity are also considered because they have an impact on how stable medications are^[77].

Pharmaceutical businesses monitor their goods during stability testing, which is conducted for certain periods of time to determine if specific environmental conditions, the quality of the final

product, or the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) (FP) have changed over time. It is carried out to determine whether or not the quality of the Final Product (FP) or Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient (API) has altered over time in a specific environment. Many considerations must be considered before a pharmaceutical or other FDA-regulated product is approved for sale and delivered to the general public for consumption. Pharmaceutical manufacturers have to be very careful in tracking how various environmental factors, such as light, temperature, and humidity, affect their products^[78,79].

The stability of medications should be the subject of several studies. The primary classifications of stability studies are as follows:

Persistent stability

Stability in the middle ground

Increased steadiness.

Stability of use^[80].

5. Challenges in developments of pharmaceutical cocrystals

Cocrystals can be filtered using several cocrystallization methods. Numerous challenges arise when using solvent-based cocrystallization procedures, such as choosing the right solvent, adjusting the conformer's and API's solubility (congruent and incongruent), dealing with concentration effects, choosing the right heating and chilling profiles, etc. Solid-state milling is better than solvent-based methods for cocrystal screening^[81]. Nonetheless, solid-state grinding in medicinal cocrystals can occasionally result in phase shifts^[82]. Among the difficulties in the synthesis and characterization of cocrystals are the formation of salts, solvates, or hybrids; the intrinsic instability of cocrystals; and the instability of cocrystals in solution phase, i.e.^[83], variations in the stability, dissolution profile, and solubility of cocrystals based on pH, ion concentration, and surfactant concentration^[84].

Thus, concerns that need to be addressed during cocrystal preparation include the possibility of cocrystal dissociation in the formulation due to interactions with formulation ingredients (excipients), the replacement of conformers by excipients, modifications to the cocrystal's stoichiometry, and conversion to a less soluble parent drug during dissolution^[85-87].

6. Conclusion and future perspective:

Pharmaceutical cocrystals are now a significant therapeutic area or research need. Numerous reviews and research articles published in different publications over the past ten years demonstrate this. Over the last several years, patents have been enforced globally by a number of pharmaceutical firms. These businesses are expanding quickly because of the laws governing them and the way they relate to intellectual property. Pharmaceutical cocrystals are a valuable and effective method for raising a drug's melting point, stability, and bioavailability that is classified as BCS Class II or IV. The primary difficulty in the cocrystal preparation process is the choice of cofomers and solvents.

In this review, order to overcome the physical weaknesses in the qualities of APIs, we thoroughly addressed the many technologies utilized in the pharmacy for cocrystal synthesis, testing, and compilation. The suggested cocrystallization methods, which will be created using various methodologies, give this comprehension of the review. In the first stages of research, classic techniques such the solvent-solvent, grinding, and slurry method were heavily utilized in the cocrystallization procedures. But as the science has developed and time has gone on, researchers have devised new ways to express how cocrystallization processes are becoming more powerful in order to overcome earlier constraints. Cocrystallization can be achieved by nuclear means

using hot melt extrusion, spray drying, laser irradiation, supercritical fluid technology, freeze-drying, microfluidic, and jet dispensing, etc.

The many cocrystal forms that comprise the medication are effectively formed using these procedures. To further comprehend the evident cocrystallization process for each approach, further research is still necessary on all of the methods. The level of attention from the medical community and academic community indicates that drug crystals have the potential to be among the most potent and significant classes of pharmaceuticals in the near future. Cocrystals have applications in the following domains:

- (i) Rebuilding current medications to increase their potency.
- (ii) Managing the health cycle using recently authorized medications.
- (iii) Aid in the operation, cleansing, and compilation of development novels.
- (iv) Integration and raw chemistry using cocrystals as intermediaries.

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